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A Creative Folio

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Espirita

(An ode to a deranged woman)

She is my neighbor, Espirita,
A wall separates us where she cooks
Cleans herself, and spends the night
Hammering things with all her might
In the dark, usually wood or stone;
In the morning, the pounding stops
And she is out tending to her gardens
Along the roads around Outlook Drive
Where she grows root crops and beans
Or weeding people's yards in exchange
For a few pesos enough to buy bread.

She lost her child to a malaise that could
Have been avoided if only she had help
But there was none and that was the start;
She suffered more abuses from men,
From her father, her lover, her neighbors;
Abuses that turn even the earth-hardened
Soul to live in a world where neither
The sane nor sanity has no meaning.

I am no rumor monger, just a listener
A trying hard poet and storyteller
Of people's lives as I imagine it to be,
So, the details of Espirita's life
Came in bits and pieces from being
Congenial with neighbors who tell stories;
It was I who came to be her neighbor,
I do not know how she came to live
At the basement of the small house next door;
At times I offer her food and she would
Always get suspicious and hesitant
And from what I gather from her self-talk
She was betrayed, cheated of the land
She is supposed to own, that was hers,

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And in this place, we are all squatters.

She outlives her contemporaries,
Save for one more very old matriarch,
They who were first to claim a parcel
Of land on this stretch of land already
Claimed by the American colonizer
And now being fought over by
The national and local government,
She still holds ownership despite being
Deranged, still strong and ready to defend
What is hers, her land, her stones, her soil.

I fear for her, as I fear for my own
Mother; some nights I could hear her coughs
Mixing with the forceful pounding sounds
But the thought of her living this long,
Despite what the world went through, Covid
(20)19 spared her, the earthquake in 1996,
The typhoons; she weathered them all,
And the changing times and technologies,
In that basement devoid of electricity
And all the comforts of a modern proper home,
Assures me, she has lived a full life.

Why don't I help her? She does not need
Helping; many a times her relatives
Came to take her away and many
A times they failed, and I am relieved
As she would not survive, surely, where
They will take her, as this place already knows her;
She has already helped herself, safe
In her world, and perhaps it is I, we
Who need help, needs saving, as I/we am/are
In an insanely sane, sinful world.

And I am a fool for telling her story
Without her knowing
Without her blessing
But let me comfort myself with the thought
That we can no longer enter each other's world
That as poet, I can only imagine her world;
Three dimensions, each separate, living separately
Colliding only when glitches occur in the matrix,
Unexpectedly.